

HYGIENIC JUSTIFICATION OF THE LEVEL OF FORMALDEHYDE IN THE INTERNAL ENVIRONMENT OF GROUP CELLS IN PRESCHOOL EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS

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According to official statistics, the incidence of childhood diseases has increased by 27% since the beginning of the 21st century and in 2013 amounted to 233.3 thousand cases per 100 thousand children, while the frequency of registration of diseases of the circulatory system increased by 1.2 times, and diseases of the respiratory system - by 1.3 times. Research conducted in recent years shows that the negative prognosis for the health of the child population is due, among other things, to the adverse effects of chemical factors in the environment. It was noted that children spend most of their time during the day indoors in residential and public spaces, including time in educational institutions (about 23%), in this regard, not only the quality of the atmospheric air in the area where children live, but also the condition of the indoor air has a direct impact on the health of children. According to numerous studies, the most likely sources of indoor air pollution with chemicals (formaldehyde, phenol, benzene, etc.) are construction and finishing materials, cabinet furniture and trim, toys and plastic products, and poor ventilation. For processing the research data, sanitary rules and norms of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 0355-18 "Sanitary and hygienic requirements for the maintenance, arrangement and organization of the operating mode of preschool educational institutions in the Republic of Uzbekistan" were regulated. Formaldehyde levels were studied in classrooms at public and private preschool educational institutions. A formaldehyde meter was used to measure formaldehyde levels. According to current hygienic standards, the maximum permissible concentration of formaldehyde in the air of residential and children's premises is the maximum one-time concentration (maximum permissible concentration, maximum one-time): 0.035 mg/m^3 . This is a limit that must not be exceeded at any given time. The average daily concentration (maximum permissible average daily concentration) is 0.003 mg/m^3 . This is an average daily level that must be maintained to minimize long-term exposure. One-time formaldehyde concentrations in preschool group rooms ranged from approximately 28.5% to 85.7%, which is normal. Formaldehyde levels are below the stated standard of 0.035 mg/m^3 .

